

DESIRES: MINOR ATTRACTION AMONG GAY ADULTS

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Desires: Minor Attraction among Gay Adults

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Abstract

Minor Attraction Syndrome is an attraction to peri to postpubescent minors, though not considered as a psychiatric disorder but illegal in social norms and law. The study's primary purpose is to discover the lived experiences, reason on their attraction to minors, challenges, fears, and realizations of gay adults' sexual contacts with these minors in Pangasinan particularly in the municipalities of Pozorrubio and Sison. The study used a qualitative research method using an unstructured interview anchored on the Theory of Sexual Offending, Maslow's Hierarchy Theory, Theory of Sexual Economics, and Social Exchange Theory. Purposive Sampling and Snowballing Sampling was used to identify participants for the study. Data collection was conducted for the month of October 2024. The study had 10 participants in which 5 were from Pozorrubio, Pangasinan and 5 were from Sison, Pangasinan and all of them had met the criteria to be participants. Their responses were analyzed through Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis, particularly the Heideggerian type of phenomenology. The study revealed that the participants had never been sexually abused as children, which would suggest that this was an immediate cause of their behavior. Participants also have a craving for sexual fulfillment, and even though they are aware that it is immoral to interact with minors, they use rationalization to defend their behavior. Another issue among the participants is the acquisition of sexually transmitted infections. Child grooming is also possible for the other participants in the near future and these minors are engaged in small scale prostitution. It is an eye opener for the situation of these gay people, the minors, the families of these minors and the those the government responsible for these kinds of cases. This study recommends more studies to be conducted to further validate these issues in other municipalities. Together with the support from both private and government sectors, with the involvement of the gay community and the families of minors and the minors alike, issues like these can be addressed to further increase awareness and prevent minor prostitution.

Keywords: *minor attracted persons, minor prostitution, lived experiences, gay adults*

Introduction

The number of articles about "minor-attracted people" has rapidly increased since 2017 (e.g., Cohen et al., 2020; Grady & Levenson, 2021; Walker, 2020). In their scientific writing, some researchers have embraced this phrase to either replace the labels "pedophilia" and "hebephilia," or to refer to anyone who feels sexually attracted to children (usually those who are 17 years of age or younger), even those who are in the latter stages of puberty or have already passed puberty. The experiences of community members who are sexually attracted to youngsters are the subject of several of these articles.

Seto's (2017) study emphasizes the idea of chronophilia, a specific sexual attraction pattern impacted by the ages of chosen sexual targets, as an umbrella word encompassing a variety of chronophilic preferences. The argument that a certain degree of sexual attraction to post-pubescent kids who are getting close to the consent age is a normal kind of sexuality makes this latter group contentious (Stephens & Seto, 2016). The chronophilias described by Seto (2017) still include teleiophilia, mesophilia, and gerontophilia, which are attractions to individuals who are typical reproductive age, middle age, and older. The terms nepiophilic, pedophilic, and hebephilic attraction are referred to as "minor attraction" in this working paper.

Seto's (2017) chronophilias model, on the other hand, adopts a much broader perspective and admits that some people may prefer older minors who may be below the consenting age (ephebophilia), older infants (nepiophilia), or pubescent children between the ages of 11 and 14 (hebephilia). Seto (2018a, 2019), Finkelhor (1984), and Ward & Beech (2006) have highlighted the growing interest in minor attraction, a concept linked to sexual offending against children, in both academic and social contexts. Recent research has shown that many minor-attracted persons (MAPs) live offense-free within the community, as acknowledged by Cantor & McPhail (2016) and Dombert et al. (2016).

Individuals often face challenges in coping with their sexual attraction due to a stigmatized social context, leading to perceived barriers and a lower willingness to seek professional support when needed. Individuals frequently struggle to cope with their sexual desire owing to a stigmatized social setting, resulting in perceived hurdles and a lesser willingness to seek professional help when necessary (Grady et al., 2018; Levenson & Grady, 2019; Lievesley et al., 2020; Jahnke et al., 2015a). Most MAPs are males, consistent with research on the prevalence of other atypical sexual interests (Joyal et al., 2015).

There is an increasing amount of data on minor attraction in communities, but according to several studies (Dymond & Duff, 2020; Elchuk et al., 2021; Freimond, 2013; Grady et al., 2018; Houtepen et al., 2016; Levenson & Grady, 2019; Lievesley et al., 2020), this data is primarily derived from samples of men within the community who exhibit such sexual attractions.

Hurtado's study explores the factors driving homosexual behavior, including curiosity, peer influence, pleasure, and satisfaction. It

reveals that gays' desire for love and belonging drives them to engage in sexual activities, a choice that occurs concurrently throughout their lifetime. The study suggests comparing homosexual behavior to heterosexual interactions and focusing on gays' subjective perceptions of sexually transmitted diseases, particularly HIV-AIDS.

Republic Act (RA) No. 11648, which Duterte signed on March 4, amends the Special Protection of Children from Abuse, Exploitation, and Discrimination Act (RA 7610) and the Revised Penal Code (RA 3815). To provide young people with better protection against sexual exploitation and abuse, the Act increased the age at which statutory rape occurs to 16 years old. (The Philippine News Agency, 2022).

There are no studies related to sexual attraction to minors in the local scale. The researcher feels that this study is a novel type of qualitative research of homosexual people's sexual attractions and experiences in having sex with young male teenagers at a local level.

Research Questions

The study's primary purpose is to discover the lived experiences of gay adults having minor attraction to male minor adolescents in the municipalities of Pozorrubio and Sison, Pangasinan, Philippines. It aimed to address the following questions in particular:

1. What is the reason why you are attracted to minors and how do you meet them?
2. What are the challenges faced in dealing with minors?
3. What are the fears in dealing with minors?
4. What are the realizations in having sexual engagements with minors

Literature Review

The evaluated articles' definitions of the word "MAPs" varied somewhat. A person who self-identifies as a "MAP" or who meets the diagnostic criteria for a pedophilic disorder or pedophilia could use it as a descriptor for anyone with a sexual interest in children. Although the term "MAPs" originated in pedophile forums and advocacy groups, it was positioned as a professional and scientific concept. Jackson et al. (2022), for instance, asserted that pedophilia and minor attraction are related concepts that frequently overlap in the scientific literature. In contrast to pedophilia, the term "MAPs" was frequently advocated as the preferred, non-stigmatizing term. According to Elchuk et al. (2021), for instance, we decided to adopt the term "minor-attracted person" for this study because it is widely used by community members and may be less stigmatizing than clinical terminology.

Jahnke et al. (2022) and Martijn et al. (2020) discovered that those who are sexually interested in minors prefer medical terminology like "pedophile" and "hebephile" to the phrase "minor attraction." However, there was broad consensus in the MAPs literature that they were speaking the language that these people favored. The literature did, however, consistently contain underlying ambivalence regarding the connection between attraction to minors and crimes against minors. Levenson et al. (2017) seems to define "MAPs" as synonymous with non-offending or "virtuous paedophiles," whereas another article used the term "NOMAPS" (non-offending minor attracted person) to differentiate between non-offending and offending populations (Tenbergen et al., 2021).

In every article, the possibility of non-offending "MAPs" was mentioned. The common theme of the reviewed publications was that there was a non-offending population that coexisted with the offending population but was distinct from it, and that both groups were attracted to children sexually. It is methodologically challenging to determine the number of people who are sexually attracted to but do not abuse children. The size of the non-offending population is unclear, according to nine of the articles. Schaefer et al. (2022) acknowledge that it can be challenging to identify MAPs who have never had sex with children since many of them are afraid to disclose their attraction to children because of the stigma attached to it and the possibility of legal repercussions.

It is widely acknowledged that such comparisons are discriminatory against LGBTIQ+ individuals, and LGBTIQ+ organizations and communities have long rejected them as being similar to same-sex attraction and sexual interest in youngsters. However, the MAPs literature frequently made the assumption that same-sex attraction and sexual interest in children are related. Levenson and Grady (2019), for example, detailed a process by which MAPs internalize harmful views of pedophilia in ways that closely resemble descriptions of internalized homophobia: It should come as no surprise that MAPs adopt these (negative) societal responses, incorporating psychologically harmful beliefs into their own identities.

The idea that sexual attraction to children is the valid foundation of a sexual identity presented MAPs as an oppressed sexual minority, even in cases where a comparison with LGBTIQ+ individuals was not overt. In ways that seem to run counter to the goals of treatment programs for men who are sexually interested in children, which typically promote identities based on normative interests and activities rather than sexual proclivity, MAPs scholarship frequently promoted the development of a positive MAPs self-identity (Richards, 2021). Lievesley and Harper acknowledged this point (2022).

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized qualitative research methodology to investigate the personal narratives of gay adults, focusing on their interpretation of their lived experiences and their contextual richness, making it an ideal method for documenting these complex

narratives locally.

According to Horrigan Kelly et al. (2016), the qualitative, interpretive phenomenological method (IPA) used in this study was based on the philosophy of Martin Heidegger. Smith and Nizza (2022) assert that understanding participants' lived experiences in connection to their social context and how they perceive those experiences is a top concern for IPA. This is in line with the idea of Dasein, or being in the world, which holds that we are constantly influenced by our surroundings through interactions and self-awareness and are irrevocably tied to them (Iwuagwu, 2017).

It documents the personal narratives of gay adults, providing a comprehensive picture of their experiences within local contexts, narrative inquiry is especially well-suited for this research (Whittam et al., 2021). Examining how gay adults' experiences effect their lives is made possible by this study methodology.

Participants

Participants in this study include 10 adult gay individuals from Sison and Pozorrubio, Pangasinan. Participants who met the following criteria were chosen through a purposeful sample process and snowballing process: (1) should be at least 21 years old and above; (2) employed or unemployed; (3) any educational attainment; and (4) had sexual experience with a male minor teenager from ages 13-17 years old.

Depending on participant and researcher availability, the researcher gathered data until saturation. Informed consent was used to safeguard participant rights during the conduct of interviews. October 2024 was the whole month that data was gathered, guaranteeing a thorough comprehension of the subject.

Procedure

The Ethics Review Board approved the research, and participants were invited for interviews. Prior to the trial, they were informed and given permission forms. The researcher maintained confidence by treating them respectfully, attentively listening, and clarifying any unclear points.

The study used informal conversation, observations, and an unstructured questionnaire to gather participant data on evidence-based practice. The Heideggerian technique was used to avoid biases. Interviews were 20-25 minutes long, with probing questions to ensure informed consent. Participants were asked about research objectives, intervention type, selection, protocols, risks, incentives, and confidentiality.

The interview was recorded with participants' consent, allowing interviewers to focus on the conversation without taking notes. The interview was documented in writing, and the researcher listened to the audio-recorded interview multiple times before transcribing and coding it to capture shared information.

The study conducted face-to-face interviews with participants in various locations, including homes and other areas, to ensure privacy and avoid overhearing.

Ethical Considerations

The investigator used a phenomenological methodology to study individuals' experiences, observing their emotions and unease during their recollections. The study aimed to educate and raise awareness, with participants consenting and rescheduling without pressure, and in-person interviews facilitating conversation and informed consent.

Upholding the values of beneficence, autonomy, and justice, the researcher selected participants fairly and with trust. Professionalism was used in the process, and prejudices were bracketed to ensure that people benefited regardless of their susceptibility.

When collecting data, the researcher kept anonymity in mind, used participant numbers rather than names, properly transcribed the results, and interacted with individuals in an honest manner. To make sure the participants were satisfied, they offered refreshments following the interviews.

Participants in the research did not face any known dangers or dropout rates, and the data would be preserved for five years before being erased. By avoiding bias in every facet of the study—including design, data collection, analysis, and interpretation—and by conducting participant-only interviews, the researcher upheld her professional integrity.

Results and Discussion

From the analyses of the data gathered from the verbalizations of the experience of the participants, there were four themes that emerged: (1) the reasons they engage in sexual contact with young male teenagers and how they meet them, (2) the challenges they encounter engaging with these young male teenagers, (3) the fears they dread in having sexual relationships with these young male teenagers, and (4) their realizations.

Having sex with minors is unaccepted in many parts in the world with laws that are designed to protect the minors and to incriminate the offenders. This study explores the psychological aspects of the behavior of these gay individuals and to give an insight of their

accounts on why they chose to do these acts.

My Choice or Their Choice (Reasons in Engaging Sex with Young Male Teenagers and How They Meet Them)

This is the first theme to emerge from this study and it pertains to the reasons of the participants in their engagement of sexual acts with young teenagers and how they can meet them. This is the part that choices are deciding factors; hence “My Choice or Their Choice.”

In the Philippines, the gay community is still in the process of being accepted. There are reports of gay individuals that have furthered in their career and are in good graces and there are also those gay persons that have been incarcerated due to their misdeeds. Moreover, we should delve further the reasons why these individuals are attracted to minors.

Fresh and Virgin

A minor is considered fresh from sexual experience and innocent. Their innocence makes them more desirable and in the inclusion that minors are also virgins. The participants have narrated that these are the desirable traits they like with minors. In addition, the participants are safe from contracting sexually transmitted diseases and their virginity is to be desired with.

Participant 1 Shared:

Fresh sila. Menor de edad sila.

They are fresh. They are minors.

Participant 2 Shared:

Gustong gusto ko ng menor de edad kasi masarap sila at fresh.

I really like minors because they are delicious and fresh.

Participant 3 Shared:

Para sa akin, mas fresh sila at alam ko na wala pa nakakagalaw at parang trophy ko sila at ako ang nauna sa kanila at walang iba na nakagalaw. Kaya safe kaming dalawa.

For me, they are fresher, and I know that no one has touched them, and they are like my trophy, and I am the first one before anyone else. So, we are both safe.

Participant 10 Shared:

Mas attractive po kasi sa akin ang mga minors.

Minors are more attractive to me.

According to other studies, sexual attraction to children is often consistent throughout life, like homo-, bi-, or heterosexuality (Grundmann et al., 2016; Seto, 2012, 2017), at least when the desire is more exclusive (Tozdan & Briken, 2019). People who have committed sexual offenses against children are commonly referred to as "pedophiles," which is a derogatory term that is often used to describe those who are attracted to children sexually (Feelgood & Hoyer, 2008; Harper & Hogue, 2015; McCartan, 2010).

According to earlier studies, there are differences in the ways that individuals who are sexually drawn to minors self-identify and deal with the stigma that comes along with this desire. Most of these studies are qualitative in character, and they often include small and/or carefully chosen samples of individuals who are attracted to children sexually (Freimond, 2013; Walker, 2020; see also Martijn et al., 2020, who polled users of several online forums quantitatively).

Desirability

A participant also shared that minors are also desirable because there are easily convinced in terms of transactions between him and the minor.

Participant 7 Shared:

Yung pinakapoint ko diyan is mas Madali sila i convince, and second mas safe po sila kaysa sa mga older na kabataang mga lalake. Mas safe sila sa mga HIV, STD, or AIDS.

My main point is that it is easier to convince them, and secondly, they are safer than older young men. They are safer from HIV, STD, or AIDS.

The act of being coerced into having sex by physical, psychological, financial, or other means is known as sexual coercion (Smith et al., 2015; American Medical Association, 1992). It is more prevalent for women and children to be the victims of sexual coercion (Sarkar, 2013; Katz Amy et. al, 2019).

Initiation and Experience

Another participant also shared that the minors are the ones initiating the motives to have sexual contact with them. Some of these minors as claimed by the participants that they are interested in having an experience with them. The minors are lustful that is why they engage with sex. It is also a way for sexual initiation for them for these minors are virgins.

Participant 5 Shared:

Kasi yung iba gusto nila magka experience sa mga beki. May mga bata kasi ngayon na mapusok na hindi mo maiwasan lalo kung ikaw nalibugan ka rin.

Because the others want to have experience with gays. There are kids these days who are so impulsive that you can't help it, especially if you're lusting too.

Participant 6 Shared:

Sa totoo lang, hindi ko naman gusto ng bata, pero sila kasi ang nagkukusang lumalapit. Hindi ako nagbibigay ng motibo. Sila ang nagkukusa na nagpapagalaw.

To be honest, I don't like children, but they are the ones who approach me voluntarily. I don't give a motive. They are the ones who take the initiative to move.

Race/ethnicity, social class, geography, and aspects of masculinity all influence how men perceive emerging manhood and sexuality. Cultural norms around masculinity and sexuality often dictate that males ought to initiate and engage in sexual activities frequently (Pleck, 1995).

Males in their early and middle adolescence may not always adhere to these scripts, and a longer transition to their first sexual experience may be cherished, according to recent study (Bell et. al, 2015). Interpreting early sexual activity may need an understanding of how desirable the sexual experience is for men (Muehlenhard & Cook, 1988; Martinez, Copen & Abma, 2011).

Communication

Participants also shared that they meet these minors using social media. They use these platforms to communicate with them and here, they schedule their meetups and the price the participants must pay for sexual pleasure.

Participant 1 Shared:

Minsan sa Facebook ko sila yayayain, minsan kapag may inuman, nakikilala mo yung mga bata, syempre kukunin mo Facebook nila tapos dun nag chachat kami.

Sometimes I invite them on Facebook, sometimes when we have drinks, you get to know the kids, of course you get their Facebook and then we chat.

Participant 3 Shared:

Ako ang ginagawa ko eh kinukuha ko yung Facebook account nila tapos dun ako mag message sa kanila.

What I do is I get their Facebook account and then I message them.

Participant 6 Shared:

Yung ibang bata kasi sila na lang ang biglang nag chachat sa Facebook. Sila ang nagyayaya.

The other kids are the only ones suddenly chatting on Facebook. They are the ones who invite.

Participant 7 Shared:

Minsan kapag may inuman at nandun sila, ayun nakikilala ko sila tapos kinukuha ko Facebook nila at dun na kami nag uusap.

Sometimes when there is a drink and they are there, I recognize them and then I get their Facebook and we start talking.

Participant 10 Shared:

Meron yung time kasi na ako rin ang nagchachat sa bata kasi type ko talaga tapos ayun ako rin magyayaya sa kanya.

There are times when I'm the one chatting with the kid because he's really my type and then I'll invite him too.

Adult sexual solicitation refers to unwanted online requests for sexual activities, talk, or personal information from an adult, whether wanted or not, to a child (Mitchell, Finkelhor, & Wolak, 2007). Adult-minor sexual interactions, such as webcam sex, sexual conversations, sending photos or videos, and offline meetings, are growing phenomena causing significant social concern (de Santisteban & Gámez-Guadix, 2017; Gámez-Guadix & Mateos-Pérez, 2019).

Augmentation of Finances

Participants also shared that the minors go to them for money. Most of these minors are high school students and are financially strained. They need money for their allowances. Some participants also shared that some of these minors need money just to satisfy their needs and engage in vices.

Participant 1 Shared:

Lumalapit sila dahil sa pera. Pag nakakita sila ng bakla ang tingin sayo pera na. Pera kasi ang habol nila sa mga bakla.

They come because of money. When they see a gay man, they think of you as money. Because they are after gay men for money.

Participant 2 Shared:

Lumalapit sila kasi dahil sa pera. Kasi yung iba naghahanap ng pang inom nila.

They come because of money. Because the others are looking for something to drink.

Participant 6 Shared:

Parang tulong ko na rin ang pagbibigay ng pera sa kanila.

Giving money to them seems like helping them.

Participant 7 Shared:

Some point meron yung ako, meron yung sila e most specially kasi nagkakaroon sila ng chance magtawag sa katulad ko if they are financially kulang.

At some point, I am the one inviting them, but mostly, they are the ones inviting me because they have a chance to call someone like me if they are financially lacking.

Participant 9 Shared:

Actually, minsan kasi sila ang nagtatawag, syempre tayo as a gay marurupok tayo so syempre part yun ng pagiging bakla. Tinatawag tayo ng laman ng loob. Pero meron yung time ako ang nagtatawag sa kanila tapos pag uusapan namin ang presyo kung magkano.

Actually, sometimes they are the ones who call and as a gay, I am fragile and that is a part of being gay. We are called because of want our body wants. But there is a time when I will call them and then when we talk about how much the price is.

Participant 10 Shared:

Meron po kasi yung iba wala po kasing babae kaya sa bakla na lang tapos yun nga swerte na lang nila kung mabayaran sila.

There are others that females are not available, so they turn to gays, and they are lucky if they get paid.

Males in the sex industry are often seen as vulnerable due to their strong libido, making "soft" sex work with bakla acceptable if the young male doesn't become bakla or effeminate himself. Females are believed to have virginity, making bakla a sexual outlet for young, unmarried males' libido, and Tan (2001) describes them as substitutes.

Participant 4 Shared:

Sa kanila nakakatulong kasi kapag bata, maraming gusto kaya ginagawa nila yun para magkapera kasi mostly sa mga bata, yung gusto nila dapat naibibigay.

It helps them because when they are young, they want a lot so they do that to make money because mostly for children, what they want should be given to them.

Participant 5 Shared:

Meron kasi yung gusto nila mag pa ampon, pero hindi ko kaya, kahit kulang sila sa financial. Gustuhin ko man e wala naman ako sariling bahay. Gusto ko man tumulong e meron naman ako pa mga magulang.

Because there are those who want to be adopted, but I can't, even though they lack finances. Even if I wanted to, I don't have my own house. I want to help, but I still have my parents.

The exchange of sex, a behavior influenced by the social context of adolescents and young adults, involves the trade of sex for drugs, money, food, or shelter, often involving multiple partners (Raiford et al, 2014; Lavoie et al, 2010). The incidence and correlates of sex exchanges among adolescents and young adults have been the subject of several research. For instance, the National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent to Adult Health (ADD Health) revealed that 3.5% of teenagers have ever traded sex for drugs or cash, with adolescent boys accounting for 67.9% of these exchanges. According to Edwards et al. (2006), there was a substantial increase in the

likelihood of the following among individuals who traded sex: using injectable drugs, running away from home in the preceding year, having anal sex, experiencing sexual coercion, reporting depression, and having an HIV/STI diagnosis.

Bottlenecks (The Challenges They Encounter Engaging with These Young Male Teenagers)

The second theme to emerge is the challenges the participants had to face. From monetary challenges, the participants had their concerns in their sexual relationships; hence, “Bottlenecks”.

Expenses

A challenge for the participants is their expenses in having these sexual relationships. They expressed that money is the language they use to get the minors to have sexual acts with them. Most of them said that by doing these, they are experiencing financial constraints especially when the payment for the services of these minors is high. The price for these minors often depends on the capacity of the participant, they do sex transaction to meet up with the acceptable price. The participants expressed that payment is crucial because if no payment was done, they might get beaten up for they did not hold on one’s end of the bargain.

Participant 1 Shared:

Ako ginagawa ko lahat para makuha ko ang bata. Kung kailangan ka magbayad ng malaki gagawin ko. Kung ang offer nila sa akin malaki, why not.

I am doing everything to get the child. If you must pay a lot, I will. If their offer to me is big, why not.

Participant 2 Shared:

Problema ko rin pambayad ko sa mga bata kasi minsan wala akong pera lalo kapag siningil nila ako.

I also have a problem paying the children because sometimes I don't have money especially when they charge me.

Participant 3 Shared:

Kapag wala kang pambayad, kausapin mo siya ng masinsinan na bumalik na lang siya.

When you don't have money to pay, talk to him thoroughly so that he just comes back.

Participant 4 Shared:

Ang problema ko kasi kapag ang mga bata nasanay na binibigyan mo na sila, dun nauubos ang pera mo. Buti ako hindi ako nagbibigay ng malaki.

My problem is because when the children get used to you giving them, that's when your money runs out. I'm good because I don't give much.

Participant 5 Shared:

Sometimes problema ko rin ang pera na ibibigay ko sa mga bata.

Sometimes I also have a problem with the money I give to the children.

Participant 8 Shared:

Lumalabas rin ang pera ko. Nag reremedyo tayo pag sa mga lalake.

My money is also coming out. We remedy for boys.

Participant 10 Shared:

Kapag may extra, yun lang ang ginagamit ko sa pagbabayad sa mga bata.

When I have extra, that's all I use to pay the kids.

Impulsive conduct stems from an insatiable need to purchase and an incapacity to consider the implications of that purchase. Even with knowledge of the drawbacks of purchasing, there's a strong want to meet your most urgent demands right now (Meena, 2018).

Burton et al. (2018) claims that emotional cravings that come on suddenly and strongly are impulsive purchases. These cravings are caused by reactive behaviors that have poor cognitive control. The instant satisfaction that a purchase offers can be used to explain this inclination toward impulsive and thoughtless purchasing (Pradhan et al., 2018).

Prostitution and sugar relationships are examples of transactional sex, which is a particular type of relationship in which financial benefit is given in return for friendship or sex. It is likely that a complex (bio-psycho-social) interplay between several elements (such as sex hormones, the need for variation in sexual experiences, and societal standards) led to its evolution and continued presence in the modern age (see Meskó, 2014 for a review). Evolutionists have instead concentrated on the factors that lead to the emergence and

persistence of prostitution, while researchers searching for proximate explanations of the phenomenon have primarily focused on the psychological, legal, and moral aspects of prostitution (e.g., Dylewski and Prokop, 2019).

Lack of Money for Payment

Another challenge the participants must face is the lack of money in payment for sexual activities. The problem arises when the agreed payment had not been followed. For the minors, it would be economic violence unto them. For the gay individuals, there would be at risk for getting punched by the minor for non-payment of the services received.

Participant 6 Shared:

Pwede nila ako bugbugin kung wala ako pambayad.

They can beat me if I don't pay.

Participant 9 Shared:

Mostly kasi sa mga bata, once na nag pledge ka, yun ang aasahan ng mga bata sayo. Kasi pag once na sinabi mo bigyan kita ng ganitong halaga pagkatapos na may nangyari sa inyo tapos hindi mo maibigay kaya minsan ang mga bakla nasusuntok.

Mostly because with children, once you pledge, that's what the children will expect from you. Because once you said "I'll give you this amount" after something happened between the two of you and then you couldn't give it, that's why sometimes gays get punched.

There are no studies related to gay individuals that are not paying for the sexual services they received that can cause physical violence on them. The researcher used literature that can be closely related for these verbatims.

Despite the obvious facts that (a) men who engage in street prostitution encounter and participate in a masculine economy of violence and threat that shapes their daily interactions; (b) many of these men form loose cliques that may engage in a variety of illegal acts; and (c) at least a few male gang members also engage in prostitution (the practice was even relatively common throughout the 1950s and 1960s), there is an artificial divide between these two sets of writings (Allen, 1980; Kaye, 2003; Reiss, 1987).

Scared and Trembling (The Fears They Dread in Having Sexual Relationships with These Young Male Teenagers)

The third theme to emerge are the fears the participants must face or yet to face. As gay people, they fear that their actions have consequences that might have a huge impact in their lives and every decision they do influences their daily living; hence "Scared and Trembling".

Fear of Retaliation

The participants expressed that they dread that the minors would report them to their parents, or worse, they would be reported to the authorities. They expressed that having these affairs of theirs is very risky and should tread carefully or else they would be incarcerated.

Participant 1 Shared:

May sometimes na kinakabahan ka kasi mga bata yan. Baka pwede ka nila isumbong, perahan kasi mga bata ngayon alam mo na.

Sometimes you get nervous because those are children. Maybe they can report you, because kids are more on money these days, you know.

Participant 2 Shared:

Nakakatakot rin malay mo mapa barangay ka, ma DSWD ka.

It's also scary when you realize that you get reported to the barangay or DSWD.

Participant 3 Shared:

Baka halimbawa magsumbong, masaktan yung ari niya. Yung ang kinakatakot ko, pero hindi naman siguro.

For example, if he reports and his genitals are hurt. That's what I'm afraid of, but maybe not.

Participant 4 Shared:

Takot ako ma DSWD. Takot rin ako sa parents malay mo makulong tayo diyan.

I'm afraid of DSWD. I am also afraid of the parents; you know we will be imprisoned there.

Participant 5 Shared:

Ang iniisip ko kung papatulan ko, kasi ako going 46 na ako, may edad na rin, ang iniisip ko kapag pinatulan ko yang mga bata, at binaliktad ka niyan, andiyan na ang DSWD o pulis, patay ka na.

What I'm thinking about if I engage, because I'm going 46, I'm old enough, what I think is when I engage those children, and they turn you over, and the DSWD or the police are already there, you're dead.

Participant 6 Shared:

Ang nakakatakot e yung magsusumbong sila sa mga magulang kasi parang child abuse kasi bata e.

The scary thing is that they will report to the parents because it's like child abuse because it's a child.

Participant 7 Shared:

Syempre, yung makasuhan ka ng child abuse o magsumbng ang bata sa ginawa sa kanya.

Of course, if you get charged with child abuse or the child reports what was done to him.

Participant 8 Shared:

Kung yung bata e magsusumbong syempre nasa sayon a yun kung pano mo dalhin yung sarili mo sa batang pinatulan mo. Sabihin na natin, maraming lumalabas ngayon na sexual harassment, meron yung mga bata na gusto nila at may bata na ayaw nila.

If the child reports, of course it's up to you how you bring yourself to the child you engaged. Let's just say, there is a lot of sexual harassment going on today, there are kids that they like it, and kids that they don't like.

Participant 9 Shared:

Natakot rin ako ma blackmail. Kaya once nag pledge ka, ibigay na ibigay mo. Once na hindi mo ibibigay, isusumbong ka sa mga parents nila.

I'm also afraid of being blackmailed. So, once you pledge, give it. Once you don't give, you will be reported to their parents.

A review of 19 studies found that about 4% of the general population is bisexual-to-homosexual. At least a third of all reported child molestations involve homosexual acts, with girls accounting for about two-thirds of victims. Teachers who practice homosexual acts are at least 12 times more apt to molest a child sexually, and with suitable corrections for bisexuals, probably at least 16 times more apt to molest a child. A review of recorded cases of teacher-pupil sexual interaction revealed that 24 (80%) involved homosexual acts, suggesting that teachers who practice homosexual acts are between 90 to 100 times more apt to involve themselves sexually with pupils than those who confine themselves to heterosexual acts (Cameron, 1985)

The Center for the Prevention and Treatment of Child Sexual Abuse and Asian partners of Family for Every Child are working on a project to gather information on sexual violence affecting boys, as victims and actors in sexual violence. The project aims to raise awareness of this issue and influence practices worldwide. In the Philippines, more boys are sexually abused than girls, but little data is available about the socio-cultural causes and impact on boys in the short- and long-term. The study reviewed responses from boys and young men who had not been abused to understand the continuum of learned behavior. All respondents stated that a major difference between how boys and girls are treated is rooted in the need to protect girls rooted in reproduction. They also stated that gender and sexuality were not taught explicitly, but rather learned from direct messages and modeling. While sexual abuse does occur among boys, the problem is far bigger for girls. Most respondents felt that the cause of sexual abuse among boys was homosexuals using their power in some form. Services for sexual abuse victims were primarily focused on girls, and accessing services for boys was difficult (Cueva, et. al, 2018).

According to Section 10 of RA 7610's penal rules, child abuse carries a maximum sentence of twelve years in jail, depending on the seriousness of the incident. In the event that the abuse causes the child's death, serious damage, or psychological distress, more sanctions could be imposed (Respicio & Co., 2023).

Fear of Acquiring Sexually Transmitted Infections

The participants indicated that they are also afraid of contracting STI's. In their minds, by engaging with minors, they are safe from these diseases but, they do not know if the minor had also contracted a disease from other people. Despite the phobia it entails them, they continue to perform these sexual acts.

Participant 1 Shared:

Naisip ko rin na baka meron sila sakit. Andun kasi yung kaligayahan pero naisip ko rin na mga bata pa sila. Kasi mga bata nagsisinungaling rin yan di mo alam kung marami na sila nagalaw na bading. Sinasabi nila virgin sila. Kaya sometimes kinakabahan ako.

I also thought that they might have a disease. The happiness is there but I also thought that they are still children. Because children also lie, you don't know if they have touched a lot of gays. They say they are virgins. So sometimes I get nervous.

Participant 4 Shared:

Nakakatakot rin na mahawaan ako ng sakit.

I'm also afraid of acquiring a disease.

Participant 8 Shared:

Bale, pag mga ganun na bagay, syempre kung sino sinong mga bading ang pumapatol sa bata, mag ingat na lang tayo. Gumamit na tayo ng protection o condom. Yun dapat ang gawin natin at umiwas tayo sa mga may sakit tulad ng Aida.

Mind you, when it comes to things like that, of course many gays have been hitting the child, let's just be careful. Let's use protection or condoms. That's what we should do and avoid those who have diseases like Aida.

Participant 9 Shared:

Yun din. Nakakatakot din kasi pasahan rin ang sakit. Kaya maging aware na lang tayo.

That too. It's scary because diseases can be passed. So, we just have to be aware

Participant 10 Shared:

Mostly kasi sinasabi nila wala pa silang napatulan na bading, pero nakakatakot kasi nga baka may sakit na sila. Kaya hindi ako basta basta naniniwala.

Mostly they will tell that they had no contact with other gays, but it's scary because they might have diseases. I don't easily believe them.

The definition of venereophobia is an excessive or unfounded dread. risk developing a sexually transmitted infection after one or more moments spent engaging in sexual activity. Due to its relatively unknown nature, very few occurrences are acknowledged and even fewer are documented (Verma et. al, 1998).

STIs have been euphemistically referred to as "social diseases," implying that societal variables have a significant role in the risk and distribution of cases of these diseases that are associated with human sexual behavior (Potterat, 1985). STIs are linked to a significant social and psychological impact (Nack, 2000). Those with STI diagnoses expressed feelings of guilt, worry, humiliation, loneliness, fear of rejection, and concern of not being attractive to other people (Darroch et. al, 2003; Duncan et. al, 2001; Lindberg et. al, 2006; Osborn et. al, 2002). Shame can result from failing to live up to expectations, from breaking a role or standard, or from an ingrained flaw in oneself that is difficult to overcome (Lewis, 1992).

A Dawn (Their Realizations)

The fourth theme to emerge are their realizations in their actions. The participants expressed that they know that what they are doing is against the law, but they continue it anyways.

Rationalization

For the participants, they justify their acts because for them, they are helping and alleviating the financial situation of the minor. They rationalize that what they did is for the good. These acts are somewhat connected to child grooming.

Participant 2 Shared:

Na realize ko na hindi ako dapat pumatol, pero nangyari na.

I realized that I shouldn't have done that, but it already happened.

Participant 3 Shared:

Alam kong mali pero kasiyahan lang.

I know it's wrong but it's just fun.

Participant 4 Shared:

Para sa akin hindi tama ang ginagawa ko pero naawa ako kasi wala sila pera at karamihan sa kanila nag aaral.

I don't think what I'm doing is right, but I feel sorry for them because they don't have money and most of them are studying.

Participant 6 Shared:

Sinu sure ko naman na safe ang pag galaw ko sa kanila.

I am sure that my actions with them are safe.

Participant 5 Shared:

May time na mistake rin yung ginagawa ko. Nagkakamali rin ako minsan kasi yun nga yung init ng katawan. May time din na mag iisip ako ng mabuti kasi meron yun time na nabayaran mo na sila babalikan ka pa rin nila.

Sometimes what I do is a mistake. I also make mistakes sometimes because that is the lust of the body. There is also a time when I must think carefully because there is a time when you have already paid them, they will still come back to you.

Participant 7 Shared:

Maybe yes, may be no kung tatanungin moa ko kung tulong na lang yun sa kanila. May yes kasi natutulungan mo sila financially. May no kasi tawag rin ng kalibugan. So far, maling mali, pero di natin maiiwasan kasi dahil sa bugso ng damdamin. Kaya minsan tulong mo na lang kahit mali.

Maybe yes, there may be no if you ask me if it's just to help them. There is a yes because you can help them financially. There's no because it's all about lust. So far, it's wrong, but we can't avoid it because of the gust of emotions. So sometimes I am just helping even if it's wrong.

Participant 9 Shared:

Mali yung mga ginagawa namin. Pero ang sinasabi kasi ng mga menor de edad e yung nga pang baon nila, so willing naman ako magbigay ng kaya ko. Pero yung ginagawa ko na pag bo blowjob, yung kapalit dahil sa pera, mali yung ginagawa namin.

I know that what we are doing is wrong. But the minors say that they need it for their allowance, and I am also willing to give whatever I can manage. But what I am doing when I blowjob in exchange for the money, I know that is wrong.

As a defensive tactic, rationalization entails avoiding the real causes of an undesirable action by providing a rational or logical explanation (Corey, 2008). Ad hoc hypothesizing and unreasonable or inappropriate conduct, motivations, or emotions are encouraged by rationalization. This process can be mainly unconscious (e.g., to construct a wall against internal emotions of shame or guilt) or totally aware (e.g., to offer an exterior defense against derision from others). Reasoning is a common behavior among people, sometimes stemming from an illusion of self-awareness. Rationalization may differentiate the original deterministic explanation of the action or sensation in question (Wagner, 2008)

As Live in Partners

Some of the participants have also shared that there are the instances that the minor asked if they can live with the participants because of financial constraints and family problems.

Participant 6 Shared:

Meron kasi yung gusto nila mag pa ampon, pero hindi ko kaya, kahit kulang sila sa financial. Gustuhin ko man e wala naman ako sariling bahay. Gusto ko man tumulong e meron naman ako pa mga magulang.

Because there are those who want to be adopted, but I can't, even though they lack finances. Even if I wanted to, I don't have my own house. I want to help, but I still have my parents.

Participant 7 Shared:

Sa akin kasi, sa ngayon, mayroon akong minor na parang alaga alaga pero never ko siyang inalok ng sex at inalok ng kung ano ano. Pero sabi niya sa akin, bata pa ako kaya respeto muna.

For me, right now, I have a minor who I take care of, but I never offered him sex or offered him anything. But he told me, I'm still young so respect first.

Participant 8 Shared

Para sa akin, advice na lang sa mga kagaya kong pangatlong lahi, kailangan mag ingat na lang tayo. Kasi may mga batang gusto man nila pero mamaya baka masulsulan ng barkada, kung ano ano na mga hinihingi. Kaya iwas na lang tayo mga kapatid sa mga bata ngayon. Para sa akin, kung may nag alok na bata na or either na sasabihin niya na alagaan mo ako, ang gawin na lang natin ay respeto na lang muna.

For me, it's just advice for people like me who are of the third race, we just have to be careful. Because there are children that they like it, but later they might be incited by their friends, because of their demands. So, let's just stay away from the children today. For me, if a child offers himself to me or they say "take care of me", the only thing we should do is show respect first.:

Depende kung gusto ng magulang. Hindi naman ako mag aampon kung walang pahintulot ang magulang.

It depends on what the parents want. I will not adopt without the permission of the parents.

A recent poll revealed that 2 million Filipino youth were victims of internet sexual abuse and exploitation in the previous year, with 96% of those aged 12-17 using the internet. The research, *Disrupting Harm in the Philippines*, revealed that 20% of young people aged

12-17 who use the internet were victims of online sexual abuse. The research projects that up to two million children in the Philippines may be victims of severe cases of online sexual exploitation and abuse. This estimate is based on demographic scales. Children described being groomed, being promised presents or cash in return for having sex and being intimidated or coerced into having intercourse (Reliefweb, 2022)

With this study, the researcher might be able to promote awareness among the gay community, public and young male teenage minors. There are studies that exist regarding on child abuse, exploitation and more, but few specifically points out to the gay community.

Conclusions

The results indicate that the participants had never been abused during their younger years which is not a causative factor of their current behaviors. The participants are labeled to be “Minor Attracted Persons.” The participants also expressed that they do not do it for love hoping that their feelings be reciprocated. Spending money for their sexual gratification puts them at financial risk because sex is a commodity. In addition, the participants are required to pay for fear of getting physically hurt by the minors. Participants demonstrated growing knowledge of what began as imprecise warning indicators of minor attraction despite that the participants know that their actions are not acceptable in social norms or even the law, they are at risk for developing antisocial behaviors and they are at risk of facing the consequences of their actions that might land them in jailtime. However, their minor-attraction attitudes did not change as time passed by. Although to avoid developing antisocial disorders, they cope up by rationalizing their actions but if left unchecked, it can take a toll on their mental health and relationships that can result to uncontrollable behaviors. The participants agree that they fear acquiring STI’s, yet they continue their habitual sexual engagement not just to minors but to adults as well, but it is too early to tell they had developed Somatic Symptom Disorders. Child grooming might be possible in the future for the participants.

Dysfunctional family dynamics is present among these minors. Poverty is the number one factor why these minors engage in transactional sex while satisfying their indulgences such as sexual urges, vices and consumer bought items from being paid for sex, comes second.

Male minor prostitution is rampant on a local scale but unreported. The summation of the factors pushes these minors to do these acts and they are sexually abused, at risk of contracting STI’s, and possibly become abusers themselves in the future.

This study makes the following recommendations for the benefit of all who share the responsibility: (1) In connection with dysfunctional family, we must create programs to instill close tie family awareness to the minors and joining them into family counselling. (2) To promote awareness among gay adults, they should also attend symposiums regarding child abuse and psychological and mental health seminars to avoid them from the repercussions of their acts. (3) The local Department of Social Welfare and Development workers should also be active in the conduct of seminars related to the sexuality and mental health and be more proactive in child protection together with the help of the Women’s and Children’s Desk of the Barangay and Philippine National Police. (4) Intensive seminars and counselling in schools must be done. (5) The government should address these issues besides from penalizing the crime committed. Intervention to poverty incidence is imperative to prevent these minors engaging in small scale prostitution. (6) To gather more comprehensive and pertinent information on the lived experiences and psychosocial status of these minor-attracted gay adults, more study among gay adults with minor attraction syndrome is required. (7) Workshops and seminars on reproductive health should be held for the LGBTQIA+ community and the research’s crucial demographic. The knowledge required to have a firm grasp on safe sex practices must be covered in the reproductive health courses and seminars. Campaigns for consistent condom usage and free, routine HIV testing must be put in place in the Philippine towns of Pozorrubio and Sison, Pangasinan, to eliminate the fear associated with getting tested for the virus.

The findings of this research can be a basis for future studies and possibly, create a theory that can specifically intersect in this kind of study and explore other issues and concerns. Studies like this can at least somehow spread awareness and preventive measures to protect the minors. In addition, in the field of nursing, this research encourages Psychiatric Nurses to be involved in these kinds of research specially cases of behavioral matters. The importance of integrating this faculty research to future fact-finding is undeniably relevant.

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